

Shakespearian Tragic Traits in Bharathiraja's Muthal Mariyathai

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Abstract

This paper will illustrate the Shakespearian tragic traits implied in the Tamil movie Muthal Mariyathai, directed by Mr P. Bharathiraja. There is always a touch of poetic emotions and sublime experiences. In the words of critics, the tragedies are nothing but a tale of sympathy. Generally, in a tragedy, the protagonist suffers a lot. Besides, there are some usual characteristics observed almost in all tragedies for instance supernatural elements, the role of conflict, poetic justice, fate, change in character, comic relief, weakness of the hero, use of irony, catharsis of emotions, etc.

Keywords: Tragic traits, Status of hero, the role of fate, conflict, suffering, weakness of the hero, supernatural elements, suffering, tragic flaw, source of calamity.

Introduction

This article focuses primarily on the development of Shakespearian tragedy as a literary genre. This paper explores the tragic traits of Shakespeare illustrated in the famous Tamil movie “Muthal Mariyathai” directed by P. Bharathiraja. Muthal Mariyathai is a realistic portrayal of different relationships between man and woman on one side, and sensitive exploration of romance on the other. With Bharathiraja masterfully helming his script and Illaiyaraaja's melodious music and acting into one sweet whole. The plot of this movie moves along in a series of flashbacks, featuring significant episodes of the dying man's life. In a decrepit hut on the banks of a river, the village headman, Malaichami (Cast: Sivaji Ganesan) lying sick (both mentally and physically), on his death bed. It includes the presence of a boatwoman named Kuyil (Cast: Radha). The protagonist is discontentedly wedded to a shrewish spouse by the maiden name Ponnatha (cast: Vaduivukkarasi) and seeks comfort and support in a friendship with Kuyil. The amity raises eyebrows, and at times socially unacceptable and complicated for both Malaichami and Kuyil. It is the talk of the villagers that he had been their headman. The villagers have all gathered at his wife Ponnatha's place pleading her to shut her upper lip and to bring him back home. The villagers are sure that Malaichami is very stubborn about not returning home. Ponnatha's voice goes up in righteous anger as to why they are blaming her. She hoped that some of the elders of the village would have left to bring Malaichami back. The mob moves to the river-by

hut and is offended on the ailing man's behalf. Not only the wife does not visit; rather, she does not even allow her daughter to come to her father.

The marriage between Malaichamy and Ponnatha is a distasteful compromise as he was a poor youth who surrendered to agree to his uncle's request to marry his daughter Ponnatha to protect the family's honour. The gloomy union results in no happiness as it seems to be foredoomed to failure. Appearances keep up though and Malaichami never breaks the promise on the deal in his lifetime. Life even gets hold of a grave rhythm under this situation until Kuyil (Radha) makes an appearance in his life.

Kuyil and her father are nomads who land up in search of a livelihood. Fascinatingly Kuyil takes up the occupation of a 'boatwoman' who assists the villagers cross the stream. She considers Malaichami with some hilarity and they have certain determined interactions. Things really transform when she finds out about Malaichami's past, and she begins to admire him. She then starts to have a high regard for him when she examines his behaviour and personality. And ultimately she feels affection for him and, he finally accepts it, after denying it initially. Nonetheless, it is all a spiritual level of love and feelings for each other. There is under no circumstances, even a hint of a sexual relationship.

There is a side plot about the love between Malaichami's nephew Sellakannu and Sevuli, daughter of Sengodan (Dalit man). When her father arranges marriage with a man of same caste, the two elope. Since they belong to a downtrodden caste, Sengodan is scared that she would be dishonoured. He comes to Malaichami for help who is horror-struck and thinks about the disgrace of the relationship between social groups, which is against tradition, and the family's honour. As he begins to search the lovers, Kuyil, who has been helping them is furious – he is more bothered about tradition. She questions whether his custom allows making friends with people of other caste. She finally asks him where his tradition was when he became a friend with her.

Better sense exists, and he gets the two married. Kuyil finds her fondness intensifying into love. In the meantime, the two young lovers are deliriously till the day, Sevuli is drowned. The Panchayat brings the demise, a conclusion as an accidental death, but her father is not satisfied. He has proof that she is murdered. While struggling for life, Sevuli bites the thief's big toe and cuts it out which is still in the mouth of her corpse which her father finds and keeps following Malaichami seeking justice. 'Enakku oru unmai therijnjaaganum Samy!' (I need to know the truth, Master) pleads the poor father, Sengodan. Malaichami stops him one night and asks why he has been acting strangely after his daughter's death. The father of the deceased shows a small box in which he has the big toe of the thief as proof and says this is not an accident but a cold-blooded murder for stealing her jewellery. Then Malaichamy finds that the thief and the murderer is none other than his son-in-law and hands him over to the police.

One day, a prisoner named Mayilvaganam, released from jail boards Kuyil's boat and reveals that he had an illicit relationship with Ponnatha during the village festival. Realising that Malaichamy's reputation is in danger, she kills him by drowning him. Thus Kuyil is imprisoned. Finally, she returns from jail to see ailing Malaichamy and on returning she dies almost at the same time when Malaichamy also dies.

In this paper, we will analyse the tragic elements used by Shakespeare in his plays such as Julius Caesar, Macbeth, Hamlet and Othello. The tragic factors that we celebrate in Shakespeare's plays are Tragic hero, Good vs Evil, Hamartia, Tragic waste, Conflict, Catharsis, Supernatural elements, Absence of poetic justice and Comic relief. I have elucidated some of the tragic elements that are employed in the movie "Muthal Mariyathai" directed by Mr P.Bharathiraja.

Malaichamy as the Tragic Hero

A tragic hero is one of the most noteworthy elements of tragedy. This type is usually a one-man show. It is a narrative about an individual, or at times two. The hero may be both gender and he or she must undergo because of some blemish character, because of predestined fate, or both. The male protagonist must be the most tragic character in the drama. Andrew Cecil Bradley, a noted 20th century Shakespeare scholar says, “a Shakespearean tragedy is essentially a tale of suffering and calamity conducting to death.”

In the movie *Muthal Maiyathai*, Malaichamy, being the village’s headman is the tragic hero who undergoes a lot of catastrophic experiences in his life. First, being his unhappy marriage with Ponnatha who always offends him for being a man of nothing. She forgets the reality that he has surrendered and agreed to marry her on his maternal uncle’s plea to protect the family’s honour. She accuses him as an irresponsible husband and negligent father, but the truth is that he is conscientious in raising Rasamma (Ponnatha’s daughter). The truth being, he is not her real father.

Later, Malaichami is again worried to protect his family’s honour when his nephew Sellakannu falls in love and elopes with a Dalit girl Sevuli, daughter of Sengodan, but fails to realise tradition and honour are not important than the hearts of the two. He gets the young couple married which fails as Sevuli is killed, robbing her jewellery by Malaichami’s son-in-law. Malaichami imprisons him. Shortly after Sevuli’s death, Sellakannu becomes mentally retarded and dies eventually.

In due course, Ponnatha finds out that Malaichami has relationship with Kuyil, the boatwoman; she creates a disgusting scene, inviting her paternal relatives’ home to threaten him. When her relatives fall short in threatening him, they leave to kill Kuyil at the banks of the river where they find a man murdered by her. The man is none other than Ponnatha’s illicit husband during her youth through whom she bears a child. Kuyil is jailed and then come out in parole after hearing that Malaichamy is in his death bed. Kuyil returns to the village, visits Malaichamy at her residence, holds his hands and they both die almost at the same time. Thus Malaichami proves to be the tragic hero experiencing disastrous life throughout.

Good Vs Evil in Muthal Mariyathai

Shakespearean tragedies engage in recreating the struggle between good and evil. It deals with the domination of evil and repression of good. Edward Dowden, a 19th century poet and critic says, “Tragedy as conceived by Shakespeare is concerned with the ruin or restoration of the soul and of the life of man. In other words, its subject is the struggle of Good and Evil in the world.” Evil, which is pictured in Shakespearean tragedies suggests its existence, an requisite and ever-enduring thing.

The struggle between good and evil is represented in this movie. Ponnatha and her son-in-law are depicted as evil characters in this movie. Ponnatha charges her husband Malaichamy being poor, married only for her assets, hiding that she had an illicit affair with another man. She always tells him that she would have married a better person instead. Ponnatha’s son-in-law marries Rasamma who is reckless and often sends his wife back to his in-law’s home to bring more money and things as dowry. As soon as Rasamma returns home, Malaichamy fulfils her needs and sends her back. He does not own a business to do or works anywhere. He is very luxurious in spending money. To rob Sevuli’s jewels, he kills her which becomes the major flaw in the movie. Fighting against him, Sevuli bites his big toe finger and keeps it in her mouth. When the villagers consider the drowning of Sevuli as accidental death, her father is discontented and goes for better judgement to Malaichamy. Malaichamy finds out the truth and hands over Rasamma’s husband in police custody.

Through these frames, we find Shakespeare’s Good vs Evil as one of the tragic elements used by P. Bharathiraja in this movie.

Hamartia in Muthal Mariyathai

Hamartia is the Greek word which means “error” or “sin”. In other words, Hamartia refers to the hero’s disastrous fault. It is an additional critical element of a Shakespearean tragedy. Each hero falls because of some defect in his character.

A. C. Bradley, who states, “The calamities and catastrophe follow inevitably from the deeds of men and the main source of these deeds is character.” The hero falls from a high position, is the result of the fatal error which generally directs to his inescapable death.

In this movie the mistake made by the hero Malaichamy is that he had married Ponnatha, who is already pregnant, for the sake of his uncle’s request and leads an unhappy life, only to safeguard the reputation of his family. The next fault is that he makes relationship Kuyil, the boatwoman and thinks that he can live happily after that. When Ponnatha finds out their affair, she assaults Kuyil and tries to kill her with the help of her relatives.

Though we do not find any sexual relationship between Malaichamy and Kuyil, Hamartia, according to Shakespeare, we find in Kuyil is that she knows that Malaichamy is already married, she loves him eternally. The next flaw that we find is when she finds Mayilvaganam approaching the village, she could have drowned him without anyone else’s knowledge but she surrenders to the police which makes Malaichamy fall ill and finally die.

Tragic Waste in Muthal Mariyathai

The hero, as a rule dies with his opponent. The passing away of the hero is not a regular death. It includes the defeat of an exceptionally intelligent, honest, intellectual, virtuous and a noble person. When good is ruined along with evil, the failure is called a “tragic waste.” Shakespearean tragedy always comprises a tragic waste of righteousness.

In Muthal Mariyathai, we find all the extremely good people dying during the movie. The death of the innocent girl Sevuli dies when Malaichamy’s son-in-law robs her jewellery and drowns her to death. Next, Sellakannu, Sevuli’s lover and the husband becomes mad and dies eventually. After the murder of Mayilvaganam, Kuyil is imprisoned, in due course, Malaichamy falls ill and finally Malaichamy and Kuyil die out of love beginning their new love life in heaven. All the good characters in this movie pass away who are considered to be honest, noble, virtuous and intelligent.

Absence of Poetic Justice

Good is rewarded and evil is punished. Poetic Justice refers to a condition in which the entire thing moves towards to a fitting and immediate end. No poetic justice is present in the tragedies of Shakespeare; rather, these plays restrain only prejudiced justice. Shakespeare understood that poetic justice seldom takes place outside of fiction. “Do good and have good” was measured an outdated ethos in the time of Shakespeare, which is why we don’t find any poetic justice in his tragedies. Good is defeated along with evil.

In Muthal Mariyathai, we cannot find poetic justice. Poetic justice is not considered to be an element in P. Bharathiraja’s blockbuster movie Muthal Mariyathai as we find all the good characters dying in the course of the movie but other people like Ponnatha who is regarded as an evil character lives after Malaichamy’s death and we find no punishment for her mistake. Another character, Malaichamy’s son-in-law who murders and drowns Sevuli, robbing her jewels is only imprisoned for seven years according to law but not penalised to death. Though we do not find his character after his arrest, we can understand that he would be released after the tenure and lead his usual life.

Comic Relief

Comic relief is our last element. Shakespeare did not follow the footsteps of his classical predecessors when writing tragedies. Comic relief was not used Greek and Roman writers. But Shakespeare desired to reduce the anxiety for the person who reads and alleviate up the mood.

Like Shakespeare, P. Bharathiraja also uses comic relief by playing some melodious songs and, for the first time, Ilayaraja introduces the kind of song called “Esapaatu” in the tamil film industry. Ilayaraja’s legendary music is one among the elements which earned celebration and laurels to this movie, which is considered as the comic relief.

Conclusion

Hence, P. Bharathiraja has exploited Shakespeare’s tragic traits in the movie “Muthal Mariyathai”. The film was decisively well received upon release. It obtained Best Lyricist Award and Best Feature Film in Tamil Award for Vairamuthu and Bharathiraja respectively at the 33rd National Film Awards. While the lead actors won their respective Filmfare Awards South in Best Tamil actor and Best Tamil actresses’ category.

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